

Mental Health Among Students

Paper Id : 18529 Submission Date : 12/02/2024 Acceptance Date : 23/02/2024 Publication Date : 25/02/2024

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.11189365

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Sunita

Associate Professor
Dept. Of Psychology
Govt. Girls P.G. College
Rampur,Uttar Pradesh,
India

Abstract

This study examined the effect of educational level and residential background of the college going girl's on Mental Health. A 2x2 factorial design was employed. The two factors studied were educational level, varied at two level, i.e. graduate & Post graduate level. The second variable residential background, i.e Rural and Urban were selected in this study. Sample consisted 40 Girl students of U.G and P.G level hailing from rural and urban areas. Two way ANOVA is used for data analysis. Educational level and residential background were found significant at .01 level. Educational level X Residential background, interaction effects were found insignificant.

Keywords Mental Health, Students, Education.

Introduction

Studies have found that Educational qualification can significantly influence mental health outcomes. (Ross, Catherine E.; Mirowsky, John, 2013) Higher educational qualifications often correlate with better job opportunities, higher income levels, and access to resources such as healthcare. This can contribute to reduced stress related to financial stability and provide a sense of control over one's life, positively impacting mental well-being. Education involves learning new skills, problem-solving, and critical thinking, which can stimulate the brain and promote mental acuity. Engaging in lifelong learning can also contribute to a sense of purpose and fulfillment, enhancing overall mental health. Educational settings provide opportunities for social interaction and the development of social skills. Building supportive relationships with peers, mentors, and educators can foster a sense of belonging and reduce feelings of isolation or loneliness, which are important factors in maintaining good mental health. Education can equip individuals with coping strategies, resilience skills, and a greater sense of self-efficacy, enabling them to navigate life's challenges more effectively. This can buffer against stress, anxiety, and depression, promoting better mental health outcomes. Research suggests that higher levels of education are associated with lower rates of risky behaviors such as substance abuse, which can have detrimental effects on mental health. Education provides individuals with knowledge about the consequences of such behaviors and empowers them to make healthier choices.

Today youth consists more than 50% of the population in our country. This is pleasant as 'Work Force' of tomorrow in nation building but an 'Alarm' also as 'Time Bomb', if we commit any kind of slackness in pondering at their will being. One of the important factor of their wellbeing is to ensure their mental health. Most of all the diseases have mental aspects and we must be serious to it when we consider national issues, quality of life of community well being.

Mental health is the balanced development of the individual's personality and emotional attitudes which enable him/her to live harmoniously with his/her fellow men/women (panday et,al,2004). Investigators found that negative affect showed declines with age in a sample that ranged from 19 to 92 year (Rossi & Rossi,1990.) Environmental factors also affect personality and achievement. The achievement of urban studies and found superior to rural students (Ameer Jaan, 1980)

According to John Guthman, 'In the last 10 years, a shift in the needs of students seeking counseling services is becoming apparent', it is assumed that among other demographic

variables such as gender, type of schooling, age and residential background would be having significant effect on mental health of college students.

- Aim of study**
1. To compare the mental health of Undergraduate and Post Graduate female students.
 2. To compare the mental health of Rural and Urban College female college students.
 3. To examine the interaction of educational level and residential background on the mental health of college students.

Review of Literature

Studies have found that Educational qualification can significantly influence mental health outcomes.(Ross, Catherine E.; Mirowsky, John, 2013) Higher educational qualifications often correlate with better job opportunities, higher income levels, and access to resources such as healthcare. This can contribute to reduced stress related to financial stability and provide a sense of control over one's life, positively impacting mental well-being. Education involves learning new skills, problem-solving, and critical thinking, which can stimulate the brain and promote mental acuity. Engaging in lifelong learning can also contribute to a sense of purpose and fulfillment, enhancing overall mental health. Educational settings provide opportunities for social interaction and the development of social skills. Building supportive relationships with peers, mentors, and educators can foster a sense of belonging and reduce feelings of isolation or loneliness, which are important factors in maintaining good mental health. Education can equip individuals with coping strategies, resilience skills, and a greater sense of self-efficacy, enabling them to navigate life's challenges more effectively. This can buffer against stress, anxiety, and depression, promoting better mental health outcomes. Research suggests that higher levels of education are associated with lower rates of risky behaviors such as substance abuse, which can have detrimental effects on mental health. Education provides individuals with knowledge about the consequences of such behaviors and empowers them to make healthier choices.

Today youth consists more than 50% of the population in our country. This is pleasant as 'Work Force' of tomorrow in nation building but an 'Alarm' also as 'Time Bomb', if we commit any kind of slackness in pondering at their well being. One of the important factor of their wellbeing is to ensure their mental health. Most of all the diseases have mental aspects and we must be serious to it when we consider national issues, quality of life of community well being.

Mental health is the balanced development of the individual's personality and emotional attitudes which enable him/her to live harmoniously with his/her fellow men/women (panday et,al,2004). Investigators found that negative affect showed declines with age in a sample that ranged from 19 to 92 year (Rossi & Rossi,1990.) Environmental factors also affect personality and achievement. The achievement of urban studies and found superior to rural students (Ameer Jaan, 1980)

According to John Guthman, 'In the last 10 years, a shift in the needs of students seeking counseling services is becoming apparent', it is assumed that among other demographic variables such as gender, type of schooling, age and residential background would be having significant effect on mental health of college students.

Keeping this view the present study was undertaken to find answer to the following problems-

- Hypothesis**
1. There would be significant difference in mental health among Under Graduate and Post Graduate female students.
 2. There would be significant difference in mental health among rural and urban college female students.
 3. The interaction among the variable- educational level and residential background will have significant effect in their respective mental health.

Methodology

Sample & Design:-

The study was conducted on 40 students of graduate and post graduate level hailing from rural and urban background. A 2x2 factorial design was used.

Tools :- Mental Health Battery by Arun Kumar singh & Alpana san Gupta was used for data collection - scale consists 130 items divided in 6 areas of mental health i.e, Emotional stability (ES), Over-all-Adjustment(OA), Autonomy (AY), Security- Insecurity (SI), Self-Concept(SC) and Intelligence.

Analysis

2x2 ANOVA was used to analyse the data.

Table-1

Mean For Mental Health Scores

Educational Level	Residential Background	
	B ₁ (Rural)	B ₂ (Urban)
A1 (U.G. Level)	57.3	67.0
A2 (P.G. Level)	55.3	64.5

Table-2

Summary Analysis of Variance

Source of Variance	S S	Df	MS	F
A (Educational Level)	244.57	1	244.57	8.63**
B(Residential Back Ground)	765.62	1	765.62	27.025**
AB (Educational Level X Residential Back ground)	8.58	1	0.30	NS
Within Group Error	1020.0	36	28.33	

**Significant at <0.01, NS Not Significant

Discussion

In the present investigation first factor educational level is varied at two levels i.e. graduate and post graduate. The table shows that F ratio for the first independent variable 8.63, which clearly reveals a significant difference in mental health in relation to educational level as it is found to be significant at 0.01 level of confidence. This significant F value enables us to conclude that educational factor significantly effects mental health, so we accept the hypothesis that there is significant difference in mental health of graduate and post graduate college going girls. The present finding corroborated with the previous findings, which could be explained as the varying levels of academic stress and pressure experienced by undergraduate and postgraduate students. Postgraduate students have more advanced coursework, field studies, and higher expectations compared to undergraduate programs. Resulting in difference in Mental health of postgraduate and graduate students.

The second independent variable for investigation i.e. residential background of the subjects is varied into two ways by using urban and rural areas. A close look at table-2 of analysis of variance clearly indicates that F ratio for residential background is found to be highly significant at 0.01 level of confidence. This significant F ratio indicates that residential background significantly affects the mental health. Thus, the hypothesis Ho2 is accepted. The distinction between urban and rural settings highlights on various factors like environmental, social, and economic factors that influences mental health outcomes. Urban students have increased access to amenities and services, and greater exposure to diverse social networks. Conversely, rural areas often feature more spacious landscapes, closer-knit communities, and slower-paced lifestyles.

In addition to the main effect of the two independent variables interaction effect among two variables are also computed and shown in the summary table of analysis of variance.

Conclusion

A look at summary of ANOVA indicates that educational X residential interaction mean square is not significant at any level of confidence. It means both factors are independent. Suggesting that the mental health of college girls is not influenced by whether they come from rural or urban background in combination with their level of education. Therefore, we can conclude that both factors—educational level and residential status—are independent of each other concerning their impact on mental health in this context.

References

1. Adler, N. E., Boyce, T., Chesney, M. A., Cohen, S., Folkman, S., Kahn, R. L., & Syme, S. L. (1994). Socioeconomic status and health: The challenge of the gradient. *American psychologist*, 49(1), 15.
2. Ameer jaan, M.F(1980); Academic Achievement of Rural and Urban Student of Agriculture; An analysis. *Asian journal of psychology & Education*. 6(1).
3. Cutler, D. M., & Lleras-Muney, A. (2006). Education and health: Evaluating theories and evidence (No. w12352). National Bureau of Economic Research.
4. Cutler, D. M., & Lleras-Muney, A. (2010). Understanding differences in health behaviors by education. *Journal of health economics*, 29(1), 1-28.
5. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mental-health-strengthening-our-response>
6. Lorant, V., Deliège, D., Eaton, W., Robert, A., Philippot, P., & Ansseau, M. (2003). Socioeconomic inequalities in depression: a meta-analysis. *American journal of epidemiology*, 157(2), 98-112.
7. Mirowsky, J., & Ross, C. E. (2003). Education, social status, and health. Transaction Publishers.
8. Pandey, V. Dubey,S.N,Rajesh,G and Ganesan, V. (2004) Impact - *Indian journal of community p,sy* pp.217-235.
9. Ross, C. E., & Mirowsky, J. (2011). The interaction of personal and parental education on health. *Social science & medicine*, 72(4), 591-599.
10. Rossi, A.F. & Rossi, T.H. (1990); *Of Human Bonding; parent child relations across the life course*, New York .Aldinede Gruyter.